

Industry 4.0 Concept for Nepal - Operating Virtual Farming Industry

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ABSTRACT: -Every aspect of human existence is being supplanted by technology as the globe continues to advance in its digital economy. Techniques using artificial intelligence are now being used in every sector of the business world. It has significant potential for expansion in both its methods of operation and its approaches. Because it plays such an important position in the organization's operations for high productivity. The achievement or disappointment of harvests is at last connected with the natural circumstances, i.e., environment, soil, climate during the yield time frames. Weather conditions have huge effect on each period of farming movement from preliminary culturing to reaping and stockpiling. Climb in worldwide temperature because of an unnatural weather change is comprehensively influence agribusiness. Present conversation centers around the impact of environmental change on horticulture to propose a virtual farming for industrialization. Sound information on the climatic factors and its cooperation with crop is fundamental for fruitful farming. The total of all technological breakthroughs in the area of agriculture allows for operating and servicing Virtual Farming using data science, artificial intelligence techniques, therefore making the process calmer. The uses of artificial intelligence and data science in Virtual Farming practices are going to be detailed in this conceptual paper.

KEYWORDS: Pollution, Adsorption, Wastewater treatment, anthropogenic, Virtual Farming.

1. INTRODUCTION

The academic field of artificial intelligence was first identified as a distinct field in the year 1955. Since that time, the field has been subjected to a number of critiques and, more recently, disappointments, such as high costs, a lack of infrastructure, and an ignorance of people. But now days, it's more advanced, with multi-disciplinary methods, tools, and a virtual environment that's been improved everywhere and even Province 1 of Nepal is under the process of e-governance [1]. In light of this, Agriculture professionals rethought its strategy, method, and process, with the goal of reducing time limitations and other physical impediments to the smooth running of the sector. In today's world, Agriculture specialists serve the role of facilitators in the process of putting together the instructions, expectations, and specifications that are necessary for managing agriculture. As a consequence of this, Data science is already mimicking the ideas, opinions, and intelligence of experts in the management of agriculture. In society 5.0, we are going

to be cared, loved and cooperated by machine as machine have the feelings. Natural environment is a gift of nature to human being. Hence it is our responsibility to protect/balance it and not to deteriorate it. Now a day we are facing climate change is the result of harmful effects of human activity. Telecommunication network like 4G and upcoming 5G has major adverse effect on biodiversity which ultimately results in climate change due to which productivity of crops decreases and farmers becomes economically poor. Due to 4G and other high radiation, population of birds decreases. Another reason for low quality of crops is fertilizer. Farmers are using chemical fertilizers and insecticides due to which microorganisms, earthworms, snakes, crabs, etc are getting killed which are very useful in increasing crop productivity and improve quality of crops. Also Government policies are so tedious that farmers unable to reach and get its advantage. Various festivals in Asia also responsible for climate change like Diwali where so much pollution created due to fireworks which affect crops productivity. Modernization is another reason for climate change. As plants are cutting/deforestation for modernization like industries construction, house/building construction, water park construction and various other activities due to which density of forest low which ultimately results in low or no rain. If no water availability, then farmers gets affected. Use of large Land for crop production is the major resource to feed and for sustainable development of human being. But now a day lands are predominantly used for modernization like building construction, industries construction etc. Due to which price of crops/vegetables increases as production is less and demand is more and reduction in greenhouse gases decreases. Soil erosion is another cause of climate change. Global warming is the major impact of climate change. Global warming is rise in temperature of earth. Forest regulates ecosystem, carbon cycle, biodiversity and supply goods for sustainable growth. Temperature rises due to greenhouse gases like CO₂, N₂O, and CH₄, etc. Due to rise in temperature biodiversity gets disrupt, fire in forest, ice melts which results in flood e.g. Glacier is most affected by global warming [2]. Loss of forest, less use of lands for crop production results in global warming. Trees absorb carbon dioxide from environment hence government started plantation program to overcome global warming. Besides these

Fossil fuels, land use and agricultural foods are having major contribution for large emission of greenhouse gases. Rice cultivation is responsible for large methane emission and large use of chemical fertilizers produces nitrous oxides. Also while synthesis of nitrogen fertilizers large quantity of greenhouse gases formed. Livestock contribute 9% CO₂ emission out of global CO₂ emission. Soil bacteria in soil converts nitrogen fertilizers into N₂O (greenhouse gas). Due to all these climate change activities millions of human being suffer from food security. Heat waves and drought condition has major impact on crop production. Recently due to climate change, there is a favorable environment for the development of insect namely 'Tea mosquito bug' (*Helopeltis theivora*). This insect eat the neem leaves and leaves gets dried ultimately tree becomes unable to grow. This situation observed in south India and Vidarbha region of Maharashtra state. Actually real host of this insect are tea plant, moringa, cashew, grapes and guava plant. Emission of toxic gases from chimney of various industries and addition of garbage/passage of dirty water from industry in river also the cause of climate change. These toxic gases are harmful to farmers and their crops too. Due to climate change there is decrease in growth period of crops and more requirement of water. Due to climatic fluctuation some warm blooded animals started to Shape-Shift their bodies like smaller appendages e.g. Beaks or legs. Due to Global warming, birds and mammals use their beaks and ears respectively to regulate the heat. Climate change also affects mountain ecosystem. Burning plastics generates greenhouse gas which results in global warming. If plastics added in farmland then water sinking in farmland is affected due to which crop production decreases and it creates water crisis. Another effect of Climate change is a storm in sea which has drastic effect on agriculture, forest etc. Due to climate change, favorable environment for various diseases in community and agricultural pests becomes minor to major. As 2020 was one of the hottest years due to which heat related illness created. Such change in temperature gives rise to change in rainfall and frequent tropical storm. Due to water scarcer deserts are expanding so it reduces land for growing foods. If temperature continues to rise then one day Arctic becomes ice free. We don't have option to change Atmosphere [3].

Atmosphere is a Colorless, odorless and tasteless mixture of gases that surround the earth. It extends up to a height of about 1600 kilometers. However 99 per cent of the total mass of the atmosphere is within 40 kilometers from the earth. This gaseous envelop of invisible film of air surrounding the earth is called atmosphere. Most of the living organisms are present at the bottom of the atmosphere. The mechanical mixture of gases in the atmosphere does not react with each other. It does have weight, exerts pressure and is compressible. As a matter of fact, the progressions that happen in the lower layers of the environment are the climatic changes. At the point when it is wanted to give the condition of climate at a specific time and at a

specific spot, the accompanying components are thought of: Sun powered radiation, Air temperature and pressure, Wind development, Relative stickiness, Precipitation, Dissipation, and Water system [2, 3].

Weather conditions aren't typical 100% of the time. A few unexpected or unexpected changes occur in climate which is called climate irregularities. They make impressive harm the harvests. Some of them are floods, dry spells, troublesome downpours, tempests, and hail storms, cols waves joined by ice, heat waves, high breezes and typhoons. These climate irregularities on the earth surface at worldwide level are called as environmental change. As indicated by the latest evaluation of the Intergovernmental board on environmental change, the worldwide surface temperature might increment by somewhere in the range of 1,40C and 5,50C over the 21st 100 years because of human exercises. Environmental change is supposed to influence straightforwardly both amount and nature of water assets. It will influence specific components of the hydrological cycle, changing stream releases, and subsequently additionally water maintenance times in supplies and water levels in lakes. It is anticipated that the timing and force of floods and dry spells will likewise change, which can make serious financial and humanistic impacts. Every one of the above cycles may genuinely influence biological system working and design, particularly on account of corrupted environments [4, 5]. MBMAN is having 26 years of dedication to standardized agriculture as professional, progressive and productive sector. As foreign employments is dominating industry over agriculture because of social constraints and high value of foreign employment in comparison of agriculture though the foreign employment is like 4P Industry i.e Pride in Public and Pain in Private as father and mothers whose son and daughter are employed in foreign job they feel lack of cared and stressed to fulfill the human needs. So, it is essential to create value in agriculture through our experience by digitalizing agriculture like other industry.

2. OBJECTIVES:

The aim of the paper is to propose unique ways for industrialized agriculture with the application of Industry 4.0 Concept for Nepal for Operating Virtual Farming Industry.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The research is descriptive in nature to document existing practices based on Farming practices and prospects in views of professionals, Academicians and Researchers. The documents and unpublished official records of Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy (MBMAN) have been referred along with key informant interview deployed in Agriculture sector in Nepal. Content Analysis has been used for conceptualizing the research. Informal consultation with IT Industry Expert, NARC Scientist and Agriculture Professionals has been done to test and validate the ideas of the project. This is action research

using Qualitative methods as grounded theory in an inductive logical way.

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

4.1 Influence on Farming and FOOD Creation:

Food creation in Asia is delicate to environment changes, for example, changeability as storm precipitation and temperature changes inside a season. Little changes in temperature and precipitation altogether affect the nature of organic products, vegetables, tea, espresso, fragrant and restorative plants, and basmati rice, microorganisms and bug populaces are unequivocally subject to temperature and moistness, and changes in these boundaries might change their populace elements as experienced from Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy, Agriculture research. Different effects on farming and related areas incorporate lower yields from dairy cows and decrease in fish reproducing, movement, and harvests. Worldwide reports demonstrate a deficiency of 10-40% in crop creation by 2100 [4, 6]. Nepali environment is overwhelmed by the west Bengal rainstorm, which brings a large portion of the locale's precipitation. It is basic for the accessibility of drinking water and water system for agribusiness. Rural efficiency is delicate to coordinate impact from changes in temperature, precipitation or carbon dioxide fixations, and backhanded impacts through changes in soil dampness and the conveyance and recurrence of pervasion by irritations and sicknesses. Rice and wheat yields could decline impressively with climatic changes (IPCC 1996; 2001) [4, 5, 7]. Nonetheless, the weakness of farming creation to environmental change depends not just on the physiological reaction of the impacted plant, yet in addition on the capacity of the impacted financial frameworks of creation to adapt to change in yield, as well likewise with changes in the recurrence of dry spells or floods. The flexibility of ranchers in Nepal is seriously limited by the weighty dependence on normal elements and the absence of corresponding data sources and institutional emotionally supportive networks. The deficit in net income at the ranch level is required to have been assessed in Nepalese challenge which is assessed in India as to run somewhere in the range of 9% and 25% for a temperature climb of 2 0C to 3.50C [6, 7]. Researchers likewise assessed that a 2 0C climb in mean temperature and a 7% expansion in mean precipitation would decrease net incomes by 12.3% for the country all in all for India [8]. Horticulture in the seaside areas of Gujarat, Maharashtra, and Karnataka is viewed as the most adversely impacted. Little misfortunes are additionally demonstrated for the significant food-grain creating districts of plain place that is known for Nepal, and slopes.

4.1.1 MITIGATION: During Professional interview, it was suggested that Strategy changes are required inside and past the agrarian area to reinforce rancher motivating forces to accomplish maintainable

efficiency development without forfeiting environmental change relief and transformation.

4.1.2 AT Worldwide LEVEL: Carry out the Paris Arrangement came to at the 2015 Joined Countries environmental change meeting - COP21. Both the text and the nation level procedures for outflows decrease, which are framed as Expected Broadly Resolved Commitments, perceive the danger which environmental change postures to maintainable food creation, and proposition important open doors for farming and the pecking order to be an accomplish part of the answer for environmental change [6, 7, 8].

4.1.3 AT Public LEVEL: More extensive social, financial and natural arrangement settings - like exchange, venture, foundation, and schooling strategies - ought to reliably uphold feasible efficiency development, in blend with variation and relief endeavors. Conflicting or problematic signs, for example, import limitations that safeguard water-serious yields, can compound unfortunate decisions by ranchers. Further developing generally strategy intelligence will be more successful than the minimal adjusting of existing agrarian arrangements as per key informant interview.

4.1.4 AT Area LEVEL: Legislatures ought to guarantee the arrangement and dispersal of applicable and forward-thinking data on asset use proficiency and hazard the board to assist ranchers and other confidential specialists with making informed interests in transformation and relief measures. Reinforcing admittance to information and hazard the board components is critical to expanding reception of manageable and useful practices. It is frequently prudent to smooth out variation and relief warning activities in existing organizations and to facilitate such activities with the confidential area.

4.2 Transform Agriculture Fields to Agriculture Industry:

After analyzing the constraints of agriculture in Nepal and significant impact of one input irrigation[9,10], We should transfer agriculture land to Data agriculture land for online plantation as Solid field convert to worth liquid in the form of Virtual Agriculture IT Industry. The objective of Transform Agriculture Fields to Agriculture Industry is to IT Agriculture Technology Development, Improve Health of society, industrialization for employment, Organic Agriculture promotion, End consumer production needs satisfaction, Solid Fields conversion in to cash liquid, Sale solid fields multiplying by time of product and Generating tourism.

Agriculture may need Tunnel for temperature control, water supply, air maintain, quality maintain which may increase Field by 5 times wider as Tunnel can extend up to 5 layers. Control temperature inside tunnel increase productivity and convert country an A/C

country making easier to work in side tunnel with a variety of production inside a tunnel which will be Easy to set/reset also. We may use Roof and wall made by bamboo (limit use plastic, pillar by iron), focusing to local resources. As shown in figure 1, Tunnel makes temperature control, water supply, air maintain and quality maintain through data of selected field characteristics, weather condition check, tunnel construction process and material used, application of heater/ventilation, assessment of security, analysis of layers expansion racks and condition of water supply along with soil condition check and robust Tunnel records/croups records. Tunnel Climate Manager may be effective to Moisture sensor, Thermal meter, and Light sensor, CO₂ and Humidity Control and Soil Sensors through IOT (climate management apps). The Climate Manager controls cold winter and hot summer months. Temperature, humidity and CO₂ is accurately controlled inside the tunnel directly day and night. The environment inside the tunnel is very dependent on the weather conditions outside the tunnel. The Environment Manager™ controls Temperature, Stickiness, CO₂, Concealing, Stowed away and Drove Develop Lights, Water system, Moistening and Manure the board for crops. Shrewd Elements Savvy and creative component of IoT Sense empowers assortment of information from any sensor alongside Security With 3 degrees of safety, IoT Sense is one of the most dependable IoT stages followed by Versatile System Equipment skeptic, operating system rationalist programming stage with open Programming interface design.

Fig. 1d: Tunnel with Smart System

Fig. 1e: Internet of Things

Fig. 1a: Tunnel

Fig. 1b: Wall

Fig. 1c: Roof

IT development should be focused as Technological tools Development as End user application development (user) such as portable application e.g. super support decision system, social learning management system along with server application and Database management for storing records of fields, customers, seeds update, customers requirement, crops updates, foods quality update, Tunnel update, location trace/ location , delivery , customer order and recipe teaching, Field management application such as planting to harvesting, Technical manpower development it worker to farm worker, Productive Fields development inputs to operation and harvest and post-harvest, Marketing Development knowing demands and collecting demands for hedging as share market by showing evidences of farm operation through virtual system or creating awareness for healthy life, Foods quality development through continuous testing and assuring using quality assurance plan, Local seeds prevention and Delivery technology development for making operation effective. We can provide option for our End user through application of developed portable application system for fields selection, crops variety entry sheet/ input selection, seeds selection(option), production require date(optional), quality requirement (optional), Delivery/Pathao, In Driver features, Quality check system (app features), live update feature and live communication (feature) and effective payment system. Let us see in figure 2.

Fig. 2. : System of Virtual Farming

Fig. 3: Outcomes of Virtual Farming

Expected results can be seen in Figure 3.

5. CONCLUSION :

It is obvious that in the event of flood and dry spell, intensity and cold waves are normal across the world because of environmental change. Their unfavorable effect on work of ranchers is gigantic. It is all the more so in Nepal as our economy is more reliant upon Agribusiness. Curiously, climate limits of inverse in nature like cold and intensity waves and floods and dry spells are seen around the same time over similar locale or in various districts and prone to increment in guaranteeing many years. Likewise, there is need to direct ranchers on projected influence environmental change and sharpen them on plausible relief and transformation choices to limit the gamble in farming area for which a virtual it based horticulture ought to

be created as a pilot undertaking to defeat wellbeing perils and client driven market.

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